

The mechanization in production organicfertilizer and soil amendment in Indonesia: case of paddy field

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ABSTRACT

The dependency of the chemical fertilizer use in paddy field has degraded the soil quality and reduced the rice productivity in Indonesia. Since 2007, the government has introduced the importance of storing back the paddy straw into the field. The organic and semi-organic farming have also been grown lately. Small and big scales of production lines, producing the organic fertilizer and soil amendment, have been available. This paper aims to describe the role of mechanization in supporting the production of organic fertilizer and soil amendment in Indonesia. It was started by the introduction of compost processing units (Alatpengolahpupukorganik, APPO)in 2005-2010. The APPO ismainly a machine to cut up the rice straw and other biomass wastes for easier degradation in the process of composting. This paper analyzes the effect of applying the disseminated machinery in the production of composts or organic fertilizers and application in paddy field. Field surveys were conducted to find the sustainability application of the disseminated APPO analyzed from aspects of technical, economical and field management of using the machine, production the compost/organic fertilizer and application the compost in paddy production.The surveys resulted in that APPO machine has been widely used in the production of compost andorganic fertilizer. The applications of compost and organic fertilizer in paddy fieldwere still in complementary with chemical fertilizers. However, the use of compost could reduce 50% of the usage of chemical N fertilizer. Further support in the small and medium production is still required to maintain the good quality of the compost product. Synergizing between the small/medium and the big industries may be needed to sustain the small/medium production lines.

Keywords: *mechanization, organic fertilizer, soil amendment, paddy field*

INTRODUCTION

Dependence on chemical fertilizers has an impact on the degradation of the soil quality (Yakin, A, 2004). The Indonesian government policy on chemical fertilizers subsidies overcomes other problems such as smuggling and the scarcity of chemical fertilizers during the planting season.Since 2007, Ministry of Agriculture Republic of Indonesia seeks to socialize the use of organic fertilizers and soil amendment with the aim of reducing farmers' dependence on the

excessive use of chemical fertilizers in the exploitation of land resources. In addition, the provision of organic fertilizer aims to anticipate global demand for organic agricultural products that are believed to have better health value than conventional products and are more environmentally friendly.

The increasing need for organic fertilizer encourages the development of organic fertilizer production in the community. The organic fertilizer productions have developed from home, community to industrial scales. The home and community scales obtain the organic materials from organic waste / agricultural waste produced by the surrounding environment; while the big scale may purchase the organic waste from several communities. The small scales tend to produce compost, while the big scales also produce organic fertilizer in form of granules. In 2018, the government subsidy for fertilizer is as much as 9.55 million tons which comprise of 4.1 million tons of Urea, 850 thousand tons of SP36, 1.55 million tons of ZA, 2.55 million tons of NPK and 1 million tons of organic fertilizer. Besides subsidizing the fertilizers prices, the government also disseminated the unit processing of organic fertilizer and composts (Ministry of Agriculture, 2018).

The Ministry of Agriculture Republic Indonesia has distributed machinery, known as APPO, for organic fertilizer/soil amendment production unit for farmer group scale. The developed model is that farmers recycle their agricultural waste for organic fertilizer and compost production and use the compost/organic fertilizer sat least for fulfilling their own needs. On land with a rice farming system, straw is used as the main ingredient of producing organic fertilizers and composts, and the products are expected to be back to paddy fields. This paper objects to presents the involvement of mechanization in the development of unit production of composts at farmer group scales.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Field surveys were conducted to find out the effect of applying the disseminated machineries in the production of composts or organic fertilizers. Twenty-seven locations of the disseminated compost machines located in West Java, Central Java, East Java and Kalimantan were surveyed. The technical, economical and socio impact on that machinery introduction were identified for each location. This research was conducted in 2009.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Field surveys

The machine mostly used for the compost production was a chopper (Figure 1). The machine is at first developed for sizing the organic waste material; however, this field survey also found that the users utilized this machine to crush the compost products. The available choppers had the specification of working capacities around 800-1500 kg / hour. However, this study found that the average field capacities were only around 60-80% of its specification capacity. This is due to the speed of manual feeding operation which cannot be as constant as mechanical feeding. In the use of a long time, there is work clutter, so that the operator slows the feed material. Nevertheless, this was not a disadvantage, because the operators were paid daily and the target processing capacity per day was met (2-5 tons / day). The average number of operators was 3 persons.

This study found that the available APPOs were operated in a plant of the composting / composting house. There was no APPO found with a mobile operation. APPO utilization in the field was not only used to chop the compost raw materials but was also used for various purposes such as chopping the forage for animal feed, mixing the compost raw materials (straw, forage, animal manure etc.) and grinding mature compost. The multipurpose applications might reduce the sharpness of the blade knife, so this study suggested to have specific implement such as hammer mills for mixing and grinding. In big scale production, the end products were in the form of granules. The government also introduced the granule machine and dryer for the big scale production.

Figure 1. Choppers known as APPO

APPO disseminations in farmer group were initially for mobile application. This model were not working because 1) the compost made from the only straw is generally lack of nutrients;2) farmers did not want to incur additional costs for chopping the straw costs without gaining higher value of nutrients; 3) the APPO in the field was mostly utilized to chop the forage feed and the mix of compost material; the compost was made from the mix of forage, straw and cow or chicken dung. The summaries of field survey results are as in Table 1.

PROCEEDING OF INTERNATIONAL WORKSHOP AND SEMINAR

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 ISBN 978-602-344-252-2

Table 1. Field survey identification on the introduction of APPO machine in the production of compost/organic fertilizer

Analyses	Chopper	Compost production	Compost application
Technical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Field capacity: 500-800 kg/hour - APPO workinghours : 6 hours/day, 4 days/month -Operators : 3 persons - Centeredplantoperation - Results : < 5 cm - Engine : 10,5-15,5 HP - Choppingmaterials : paddystraws andforages, compost 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Materials : 60-80% cowdung, <20% paddy Straw, sawdust, biochar -materials : fromsurrounding - Production : up to70 tons/month - metode: open windrowcompositing, manual turn 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Composts markets : paddy fields & unirrigated fields -Compost dossage in paddy field : 600-1400 kg/ha -Reduction of chemical fertilizers : 50%-100% -Paddy production : 5-9 ton/ha -Straw utilization: 90% back to the field, 10% for feed
Economical	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Chopping cost : Rp 270/kg (67% operator + 33% diesel oil) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Operational cost of compost production: Rp 425-550/kg (included chopping cost) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Saving at least urea up to 50%
Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> APPO managed by farmers group 		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Compost applications in Paddy fields were mostly usedby the farmers understanding SRI program
Opportunity and Challenge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -APPO modification : mobile APPO 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compost production : Mostly successful in integrated paddy-livestock system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Farmers are aware of soil degradation caused by the excessive use of chemical fertilizer - Farmers concerns about fertilizer subsidy cut off - Awareness program such as SRI or PTT

OPPORTUNITIES

This study shows that some existing APPOs have not been able to operate optimally due to technical and non-technical factors. However, there are opportunities for optimal use of APPOs in farmer groups, where there arean integration of crops and livestock. The raw materials for producing compost were 60-80% of livestock manure while straws were only 10-20% (Figure 2).

Figure 2. APPO utilization in crop-livestock integration

The APPO utilization in conditions such as Figure 2 was projected on the farmer groupscale or small business enterprise. Besides fulfilling the group needs, organic fertilizers should be directed to be sold on the market. The farmer consideration in compost application on paddy field was supported by the awareness of their soil quality degradation (Pickering et al., 1997; Pattley et al., 1997). Though at this moment the use of organic fertilizers in paddy production is generally still in complementary with chemical fertilizer.

The improvement of the management system of farmer groups in production of organic fertilizer needs to be continued so that these farmer groups can be incorporated in the market chain of the compost/organic fertilizer producer. Competition with large private factories which also produce organic fertilizer would turn off this small scale business. The government efforts to improve the link between small-big scale enterprises should be continued. The sustainability of production continuity can reduce the inorganic fertilizer applications.

CONCLUSIONS

The use of organic fertilizer in paddy field could reduce the urea 50-100%. The chopper known as APPO has been used by the farmers group to recycling their organic waste to produce composts. This study conclude that the sustainability production of compost in farmers groups depends on the availability of raw materials, mainly manures. Farmers prefer composts made

by 60-80% of livestock manure, while the paddy straw for compost raw material was only about 20%.

Another challenge in the sustainable production of compost was the market. The big companies sold the subsidized compost. This resulted in the selling prices of farmer products were higher than big company products. This study suggested synergies between small-big enterprises to maintain the sustainable production of composts in group farmers. The big scales might purchase the bulk composts from the farmer groups to be processed further into granules.

Anticipation to the government subsidy removal on chemical fertilizer prices and the knowledge from the government programs such as SRI (system of rice intensifications) and PTT (Pengelolaan tanaman terpadu, integrative plant management system) supported the use of organic fertilizers in paddy field.

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